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Coming out and normative shifts: Investigating usage patterns of *gay* and *homosexual* in a corpus of news reports on Ricky Martin

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Abstract

This study seeks to shed light on discursive shifts in sexuality-related normativity that are associated with coming out. Subscribing to a queer linguistically informed type of critical discourse studies, it investigates the usage patterns of two labels that are commonly used to denote same-sex sexualities: *gay* and *homosexual*. The meanings and usages of these forms are first discussed more generally, based on evidence from an earlier study on a major English reference corpus. The analytical part studies the usage patterns of the two terms in a corpus of news reports on Ricky Martin more specifically, through a systematic inspection of concordance lines. For this purpose, the usages of the two forms are analysed in and compared across two sub-corpora, one with texts dating from before and one with texts dating from after the artist's public coming out as a gay man. Besides a quantification of the terms in the two corpora, the main focus is on the qualitative analysis of the usage patterns that the terms exhibit in the data. The patterns thus identified are discussed in

relation to the discursive construction of coming out as a central experience of non-heterosexual people and as discursive evidence for normative shifts associated with coming out.

Keywords: news coverage; coming out; language and sexuality; Ricky Martin; pop music; critical discourse studies; normativity; gay masculinity

1. Introduction

Although coming out is widely perceived to be a decisive event in the lives of non-heterosexual people, we still know very little about the discursive consequences of this process. Do we treat, conceptualise and discursively construct social actors differently once they have gone through coming out? Does a coming out have an effect on the normative mechanisms through which we view people? And if so, how does this surface in our linguistic choices? This paper sets out to provide initial answers to these questions, using the discursive construction of Latino pop star Ricky Martin as a case study.

Born in 1971 in Puerto Rico, Ricky Martin achieved early fame as a member of the boy band Menudo, and has become a successful solo artist since 1991. Even though his sexuality had been questioned in the international media for some time (see Quiroga 2000: 181-190), Martin came out publicly fairly late in his career, posting on his blog and on his Twitter account on 29 March 2010 that he is gay. Sexual normativities have (beside other types of normativity, see Negrón-Muntaner 2004: 247-271) for a long time played a central role in the public discursive construction of Ricky Martin, even in times before his coming out (see, for example, Calafell 2007: 100-111; Lugo-Lugo 2012, Rivera Santana, Vélez Agosto, Benozzo and Colón de la Rosa 2014). The extent of the reception of Martin's coming out is probably unprecedented, thus making it a potentially highly influential, though clearly atypical, coming out, due to its global scale and Martin's operating from a privileged position.

The central goal of the present study is to investigate whether and how this public coming out has changed the way language is used in news media to write about Ricky Martin. To this end, I conduct a queer linguistically informed critical discourse analysis involving a systematic and mainly qualitative linguistic analysis of the media coverage pre- and post-dating the coming out of the artist. At the theoretical level, the findings will be discussed in relation to queer linguistics, sexual normativity and the discursive construction of coming out.

2. Language, coming out and normativity

The fact that language use shapes the ways we conceptualise sexuality in terms of identities, desires, relationships and normativity has for a long time been recognised in queer linguistics (Motschenbacher 2010, 2011). This is a research strand that critically investigates potentially harmful sexuality-related discourses, many of which have become so naturalised that they are in general not questioned (for example, gender- and sexuality-related binarisms and concomitant asymmetries, Davis, Zimman and Raclaw 2014; female-male difference thinking, Cameron 2013; heteronormativity; Leap 1999: 436). Queer linguistics cultivates a scepticism towards categories and, more specifically, identity categories, criticising the way they may cause ignorance of intra-categorical heterogeneity, exclusion, marginalisation of less prototypical category members, and a stigmatisation of non-

conforming practices. A great deal of this focus is normativity-related or, to be more precise, anti-normative, that is, queer linguistics questions normativities that are likely to have these discursive (and social) effects (Motschenbacher 2014, forthcoming b).

Coming out may, on the surface, appear as a transgressive, and therefore, anti-normative speech event. This is because it involves a self-affirmative claiming of an identification that is traditionally considered non-normative. However, a closer inspection of coming out reveals that its queer potential is at best limited. This is the case because it supports rather than challenges dominant notions such as in vs. out or hetero vs. homo (Morrish and Sauntson 2007: 98; Zimman 2009: 54), that is, binarisms that are in general questioned by queer linguists. At the same time, a reading of coming out as non-normative ignores that traditionally less accepted sexualities in Western societies have often undergone a certain degree of normalisation. As a consequence of this, they have developed normativities of their own, for example, homonormative discourses that stipulate what gay men and lesbian women are (supposed to be) like. Coming out is structured by regulatory frames that dictate what can(not) (easily) be publicly expressed in terms of sexuality (see Butler 1990). These regulatory aspects are not stable but, rather, are historically and culturally variable. For example, coming out as a gay man or a lesbian woman has lost some of its stigma or sensation value in many Western societies due to a normalisation and increasing public recognition of these sexualities as legitimate. However, research demonstrates that the closet and coming out continue to be experiences that gay men and lesbian women regularly orient to in everyday interactions. Thus, non-heterosexual identity constructions are still perceived as marked in comparison to heterosexual ones (Kitzinger 2005, Land and Kitzinger 2005, 2007).

Even though coming out is popularly perceived as an act of revealing a hidden truth, from a post-modernist perspective it is probably more adequate to say that it is associated with a discursive re-construction of what is seen as the truth, as there is no such a thing as an absolute truth that is unmediated by the shaping power of discourses. From the point of view of speech act theory, coming out has been described as a communicative act that does not just represent a particular reality, but significantly changes reality, as pointed out by Liang:

“Coming out is therefore a speech act that not only describes a state of affairs, namely the speaker's gayness, but also brings those affairs, a new gay self, into being. By presenting a gay self, an individual alters social reality by creating a community of listeners and thereby establishing the beginnings of a new gay-aware culture. Coming out is, in this respect, a performative utterance (Austin 1962) that can be seen as revolutionary.” (Liang 1997: 293)

At the same time, a coming out marks a normative shift in the sense that it changes the expectations that society projects onto a person:

“[T]o ‘come out’ is to expose oneself to a different set of dangers and constraints, to make oneself into a convenient screen onto which straight people can project all the fantasies they routinely entertain about gay people, and to suffer one’s every gesture, statement, expression, and opinion to be totally and irrevocably marked by the overwhelming social significance of one’s openly acknowledged homosexual identity.” (Rivera Santana, Vélez Agosto, Benozzo and Colón de la Rosa 2014: 189)

It is the discursive effects that are associated with this “new gay-aware culture” and with the concomitant submission to “a different set of dangers and constraints” that are the subject of this study.

Previous sociolinguistic and discourse analytic research has studied coming out from a range of perspectives, with the dominant share concentrating on the genre of the coming-out narrative

(Sauntson 2015) and its formal and functional make-up (e.g. Bacon 1998, Liang 1994, 1997, Morrish and Sauntson 2007: ch.2, Wong 2009, Wood 1997). Among other aspects investigated by such research are the status of coming out as a speech act (Chirrey 2003), coming-out advice literature, websites and training (Chirrey 2011, 2012, Didomenico 2015), coming out and outing processes in the media (Bannink and Wentink 2015, Morrish and Sauntson 2007: ch.6), and coming out in educational contexts (e.g. Ellwood 2006, Morrish and Sauntson 2007, Ó'Móchain 2014, Sauntson 2007). In media and communication studies, one also finds some recent work on celebrities publicly coming out (for example, Benozzo 2013 studies the coming out of an Italian pop star), with most studies investigating the coming out of gay male athletes (e.g. Kian, Anderson and Shipka 2015, King 2017, Magrath, Cleland and Anderson 2017, Schallhorn and Hempel 2015), maybe because professional sport (and especially male team sports) is a context in which traditional hegemonic masculinities are still highly valued and same-sex affection is viewed as a threat (see Nylund 2004). Popular culture and the pop music industry, by contrast, are associated with a longer tradition of exploring gender and sexuality more progressively (Kian, Anderson and Shipka 2015: 621-622). However, as the lateness of Ricky Martin's coming out shows, even in the area of pop music, a coming out bears risks in terms of a potential loss of support from certain target audiences. Previous research has documented coming out related norms as evident from the discourses writers draw on in coming out advice literature (Chirrey 2012). These norms tend to sketch out coming out as "a liberating, self-actualising action, which, although it may be hard and risky, is fundamentally a positive and rational step." (Chirrey 2012: 39). More generally, the discursive construction of coming out has been found to be commonly associated with discourses of confession, liberation, identity, pride and authenticity (e.g. Rivera Santana, Vélez Agosto, Benozzo and Colón de la Rosa 2014: 183).

While earlier studies of coming out look either at the process of coming out itself or at communicative practices that follow a coming out, the present study seeks to shed new light on the issue by incorporating text material dating from both before and after the coming out. This allows us to perform direct comparisons between the two time periods, which yield evidence of what has changed.

3. Methodological considerations

This study is a component of the LIDISNO project – a project that is dedicated to the study of "Linguistic Dimensions of Sexual Normativity" and is currently being carried out at Florida Atlantic University and Goethe-University Frankfurt am Main. It uses the framework of critical discourse studies (Machin and Mayr 2012, Motschenbacher 2018a) to take a scrutinising look at sexuality-related discourses surfacing in language use and draws on textual material from a specifically compiled corpus of news reports on Ricky Martin. Two sub-corpora with text data from before and after Martin's public coming out are compared. The material was retrieved from LexisNexis, searching for English-language news media publications with the name *Ricky Martin* in the headline. Of the approximately 1,800 articles thus retrieved, many had to be eliminated from the corpus, either because on manual inspection they proved not to be centrally about Ricky Martin, or because they were duplicates. Interview transcripts were also excluded to make the dataset internally more homogeneous. This leaves us with a final corpus of 1,004 newspaper articles and online news texts, a total of 346,971 word tokens. The BEFORE sub-corpus contains 393 texts and 158,128 word tokens; the AFTER sub-corpus contains 611 texts and 188,843 word tokens.

The cleaning-up of the data gained from LexisNexis showed that journalistic texts are often published (and read) across national boundaries. This makes it difficult to categorise a text as a product of a particular culture. Still it is probably adequate to say that the majority of the texts are originally from North American, Asian, Australian and European sources. There is a notable absence of texts from Africa, which is not among Martin’s target markets, and South America, where the media generally publish on Ricky Martin in Spanish rather than English. In terms of the newspaper category, the majority of the corpus texts are articles from nationally and internationally read broadsheet newspapers.

Coverage of Ricky Martin is not distributed equally across the years (see Table 1). The texts in the BEFORE corpus date from 1998 to 28 March 2010, while those in the AFTER corpus date from 29 March 2010 to 15 January 2018. The high public recognition of Martin’s coming out can be estimated to some extent from the fact that the two years before the coming out show article frequencies of 22 (2008) and 6 (2009) articles per year – a frequency that rises to 84 articles in 2010 during the nine months after Martin’s coming out. If this figure is extrapolated to the full year, the frequency for 12 months amounts to 112, which is the highest article density of all years investigated.

Table 1: Distribution of texts in the BEFORE and AFTER corpora

BEFORE		AFTER	
YEAR	Texts	YEAR	Texts
1998	6	2010 AFTER	84
1999	83	2011	74
2000	61	2012	50
2001	24	2013	50
2002	7	2014	74
2003	27	2015	89
2004	14	2016	107
2005	56	2017	65
2006	39	2018	18
2007	42		
2008	22		
2009	6		
2010 BEFORE	6		
total	393 texts		611 texts

The analysis concentrates on the usage patterns of the terms *gay* and *homosexual* in the Ricky Martin news text corpus. The selection of these terms is motivated by the findings of an earlier, quantitative corpus linguistic study on the same dataset (Motschenbacher 2019), which showed that the semantic domain of sexual identity is strongly overlexicalised in AFTER when compared to BEFORE, where no forms from this semantic domain turn out to be (statistically based) keywords. The two terms from this semantic domain with the highest keyness rankings in AFTER are *gay* (ranking second) and *homosexual* (ranking twentieth) are subjected to an in-depth qualitative analysis that concentrates on the inspection of concordance lines (but see Motschenbacher 2019 for an analysis of full texts from the dataset).

The study seeks to address the following research questions: Do the usage patterns of the two central sexual descriptors change in the media coverage after Ricky Martin’s coming out? And if this is the case, for which discursive shifts do these changes provide evidence? The findings will be

discussed in terms of their implications for shifts in sexual normativity between the pre- and post-coming-out phases.

4. Sexually descriptive adjectives: Meaning and usage

Sexually descriptive adjectives (like *gay*, *lesbian*, *bisexual*, *homosexual*, *heterosexual*, *straight*, *same-sex*, *queer*) are a central component of the discursive construction of sexuality, since they are linguistic tools that we use to classify sexual identities, desires, relationships, practices and other sexuality-related aspects. However, these adjectives are not all used to the same extent for the classification of these aspects. For example, some may be more strongly associated with the discursive construction of sexual identity, while others may play a more central role in the construction of sexual practices, and this is reflected in the usage patterns of these forms. A recent corpus linguistic study of sexually descriptive adjectives (Motschenbacher 2018b) revealed to which aspects the individual adjectives are more strongly connected, based on their collocational behaviour in the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA). These connections are visualised in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual map of sexual descriptive adjectives, based on collocation analysis of COCA data (Motschenbacher 2018b)

We can see in Figure 1 that the eight sexual descriptors analysed yield anything but a binary picture. Rather, they form a complex lexical field with overlaps and specificities in the usage patterns of the individual forms. For example, while the adjective *queer* is mainly used to talk about sexual identity, sexual politics and academic matters, the form *same-sex* is predominantly used as a classifying device for sexual practices, relationships and desires. The nominal collocations of the two forms studied in Section 5 are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Nominal collocates directly following *gay* and *homosexual* in COCA (# indicates collocate rankings; Motschenbacher 2018b)

Adjective	Nominal collocates by conceptual category
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gay	<p>Identity (8): #4 people, #5 community, #15 person, #20 characters, #23 culture, #26 parents, #28 lifestyle, #30 youth</p> <p>Politics (7): #3 rights, #10 activists, #11 pride, #19 activist, #24 issues, #25 bashing, #27 liberation</p> <p>Relationship (6): #1 marriage, #7 couples, #12 marriages, #14 couple, #18 friends, #29 relationships</p> <p>(Male) Gender (5): #2 men, #6 man, #8 male, #21 males, #22 guy</p> <p>Practice (1): #17 sex</p>
homosexual	<p>Practice (7): #1 acts, #2 behavior, #4 conduct, #5 activity, #14 sex, #19 experience, #20 practices</p> <p>Identity (7): #10 community, #11 persons, #13 lifestyle, #18 teacher, #24 identity, #26 teachers, #27 person</p> <p>Relationship (6): #6 relations, #8 marriage, #9 couples, #15 relationships, #16 relationship, #23 unions</p> <p>Politics (4): #7 rights, #17 stigma, #21 agenda, #30 activists</p> <p>Desire (4): #12 orientation, #22 desire, #28 love, #29 inclination</p> <p>(Male) Gender (2): #3 men, #25 man</p>

We can see that the adjective *gay* is mainly used to describe sexual identities, politics, relationships, and masculinities. Identity and relationship are also prominent categories for *homosexual*. Sexual politics and masculinity are less central to this adjective than for *gay*. On the other hand, it is commonly used as a descriptor for aspects in the domains of sexual practices and desire – domains that are underrepresented, or even absent, with *gay*. The fact that both adjectives collocate with male rather than female nouns suggests that both have a strong socially male bias. This is true even though they are lexically gender-neutral and could in principle also be used to describe female referents. According to these findings, gayness is mainly conceptualised as something that people are, as something that can be politicised, as a sexual relationship type and as a particular type of masculinity. Meanwhile, *homosexual* is commonly used to describe an identity, sexual practices, relationships, and, somewhat less centrally, desires and politics.

Compared to *gay*, which is today commonly used in neutral to positive contexts, *homosexual* is a problematic term. This is because it possesses technical, pathological and, thus, negative connotations that normally disqualify it from being used as a positive in-group identity label or in self-identification. It tends to occur in out-group contexts. Heterosexual people may talk about same-sex identified people using the term to convey psychological distance from the referent (*He is (a) homosexual*). Self-affirmative statements like *I am (a) homosexual* tend to sound odd in most contexts and may therefore be used for comical effects (as, for example, in the film *But I'm a Cheerleader*, which makes fun of homosexual therapy). The term is particularly denigrating when it is used for the description of people. It may be deemed slightly more acceptable to describe behaviours or desires as *homosexual* (see also Motschenbacher forthcoming a).

5. Usage patterns of *gay* and *homosexual* in the Ricky Martin Corpus

5.1 Analysis of frequencies

The software AntConc (Anthony 2018) was used to identify the frequencies of the forms *gay* and *homosexual** (in the search query, the asterisk stands for all letter sequences of size zero or more) and to produce concordance lines of the two terms in the BEFORE and AFTER corpora. All concordance lines were inspected to detect functional usage patterns as evident from the semantics of lexical items in the syntactic environments of the terms.

Of the sexual identity labels that turn out key in AFTER (Motschenbacher 2019), the relatively value-neutral term *gay* is clearly most common, with 479 occurrences in AFTER, while the semantically more negative form *homosexual** occurs 94 times. On first glance, this leaves the impression of a fairly acceptable representation of same-sex sexualities overall in the more recent corpus. However, what is clearly less positive is the historical development of these frequencies. Even though Ricky Martin was not publicly out when the texts in BEFORE were created, his (potentially) being gay is a common topic in the earlier corpus data. The semantically more positive term *gay* occurs 83 times in BEFORE; semantically more negative word-forms starting with *homosexual** occur 6 times. It is only expectable that the frequencies of the two terms rise after a public coming out. But what is noteworthy is that the rate of this increase is much higher for the more negative term *homosexual**, whose frequency in AFTER is 25 times higher than that in BEFORE, while *gay* only occurs 5.5 times more often in AFTER than in BEFORE. If we assume that later periods are associated with a greater acceptance of same-sex sexualities, it must, at this point, remain counter-intuitive that the more negative form shows a stronger growth. The qualitative analysis of the usage of *homosexual** in AFTER in Section 5.3 will shed more light on this.

Table 3: Frequencies of *gay* and *homosexual** in BEFORE and AFTER

	BEFORE	AFTER
<i>gay</i>	83	456 (increase by 5.5 times)
<i>homosexual*</i>	6	150 (increase by 25 times)

5.2 Concordance lines of *gay* and *homosexual* in BEFORE

Even though *homosexual** occurs rarely in BEFORE, the negativity, and thus heteronormativity, of the term is easily illustrated when looking at data extracts from the corpus:

(1)

[...] *pulling off* a look that has up to now been regarded as either totally **homosexual** or ethnically *slimy* in a sexist way, i.e. *get a load of Sergio Valente at the bar over there, ohmigod, who does he think he is?* [Hamilton Spectator, 29.05.1999]

(2)

[...] *gay* community, pretty much everybody thinks he is -- he just comes across as a **homosexual** male. But maybe that's people wanting to think he's gay." [Calgary Herald, 11.03.2000]

In extract 1, the adjective *homosexual* is used in syntactic proximity to (other) semantically negative adjectives (*slimy*, *sexist*) and derogative informal vocabulary (*pulling off*, *load*). In extract 2, the sentence *he just comes across as a homosexual male* is remarkable for its use of the hedge *just*. The

use of this mitigating device indicates the negativity of the statement it conveys. It is also noteworthy that the noun *male* rather than *man* is chosen in this context. This choice is compatible with the connotations of *homosexual*, as the noun *male* has more formal, clinical and depersonalising connotations than *man*, which give the phrase *a homosexual male* a clearly distancing function.

In a similar vein, *gay* is used in BEFORE in a way that resembles heteronormative policing behaviour. The form occurs frequently in contexts where the heteronormative pressure on Martin surfaces in speculations about his potential non-heterosexuality. In the following data extract, for example, Martin is quoted lamenting his helplessness in the face of heteronormative pressures:

(3)

*I could have been married with kids for years or have 27 girlfriends, and if people still want to go around saying that I'm **gay**, they will. Whether I've been with a cow, a broom, an aeroplane, or with a woman, it's no one's business. [Mirror, 09.12.2000]*

Linguistically, speculations about Martin's potential same-sex identification are typically expressed by descriptions of the press and other social groups bothering Martin with sexuality-related questions (4), references to *rumors* (5), *gossip* (6), *speculation* (7), or their grammatical expression in the shape of subjunctive forms within hypothetical *if*-clauses (8), descriptions of Martin's behaviour as *gay* (9), juxtapositions of *gay* and heterosexual information as competing discourses (10), or reporting on instances in which Martin has been outed by other people against his will (11):

(4)

*Then there's the gay community. "Is Ricky Martin **gay**?" is a question asked regularly in the mainstream press and by fans on Internet [...] [Calgary Herald, 11.03.2000]*

(5)

*[...] Martin, whose "Sound Loaded" album was released this month, won't confirm or deny rumors that he's **gay**. He simply says he's happily single. [St. Petersburg Times, 26.11.2000]*

(6)

*Gossip columnists have often identified Martin as **gay**, but he has refused to comment on his sexuality. [Deutsche Presse-Agentur, 20.08.2008]*

(7)

*[...] discussing his love life. He once appeared on the cover of *The Advocate*, a **gay** magazine, fuelling speculation about his sexuality. In the interview, he playfully dodged questions [...] [National Post Canada, 21.05.2003]*

(8)

*[...] there has been no official word on Martin. What does your sexual intuition tell you? And if Martin were **gay**, and if it were to be publicly known, do you think it would have a negative effect on his career? [Hamilton Spectator Ontario, 29.05.1999]*

(9)

*I think his dance is kinda **gay**. But he'll stay on top because of fan reaction and he's popular [...]*
[Vancouver Province, 09.03.2000]

(10)

*[...] other rumour circulating about Ricky, which seems to contradict the one that he's **gay**, is that he is actively looking for a wife. [Mirror, 09.12.2000]*

(11)

*According to a Hollywood skincare guru, Ricky Martin is **gay**. Ole Henriksen told an unnamed Swedish magazine: "He is a bit more open about it these days than he used to be. [...]" [New Zealand Herald, 12.12.2007]*

Looking at extracts (9) and (10), it is noteworthy that they linguistically construct heterosexuality as a matter of desire rather than identity. That is, it is specified that women desire Martin (*the way women react*) and that Martin desires women (*he is actively looking for a wife*), while sexual identity labels like *heterosexual* or *straight* are not used. This contrasts markedly with the construction of Martin's same-sex sexuality, which is frequently achieved through use of the terms *gay* and *homosexual** as identity labels.

The BEFORE corpus also regularly exhibits passages in which Martin's, and sometimes other people's, reactions to inquisitive behaviour on the side of the media are described. Major reaction types that can be verified in the data include constructions of Martin's denial that he is gay (12-13), of his claims that sexual orientation does not matter (14-15), of his avoidance of talk about sexuality altogether (16-17; see also Calafell 2007: 108 or Lugo-Lugo 2012: 259-260 on this tactic of de-sexualisation), or the portrayal of people providing proof of Martin's heterosexuality (18):

12)

*Martin has long denied rumors that he is **gay**, despite having a large gay fan following. [UPI, 20.08.2008]*

(13)

*The *Living on a Prayer* singer - who recently rejected claims he is **gay** - said: "My ideal girl is someone who's stubborn. I'd never go for [...]" [Daily Record, 11.05.2000]*

(14)

*I don't think I should have to tell anyone if I am **gay** or not, or who I've slept with or not. Sure, I have a big **gay** following, but when I'm singing I don't have girls or boys or horses or grandparents in mind [...]" [Mirror, 09.12.2000]*

(15)

*[...] comes to sex - and I'm talking about myself, I'm talking about straight, **gay**, lesbian, it doesn't matter. "Life is too short not to be happy," he [...]" [The Gazette (Montreal), 20.03.2000]*

(16)

*[...] singer revealed that he was not bothered by people persistently asking if he is **gay** - and he refused to deny or confirm allegations about his sex life. [The Mirror, 30.11.2000]*

(17)

*Puerto Rican news media have long speculated Martin is **gay**, but he has avoided commenting on the topic. [Globe and Mail, 31.03.2007]*

(18)

*"Every time was unforgettable." Adriana revealed hunky Ricky has a growing army of **gay** fans - and has been dogged by rumours that he is **gay** too. But she insisted: "I can assure you that Ricky is man, all man [...]" [People, 18.07.1999]*

The discursive construction of evasive behaviours contributes to the effect of a victimisation discourse that sees society or the media as the aggressor and Martin as the victim of such inquisitive attacks, who cannot talk about his gay identity because he has to fear social sanctions. If one wanted to ascribe a higher degree of agency to Martin's persona, an alternative reading might be in terms of "disidentification", which Muñoz defines as "a performative mode of tactical recognition that various minoritarian subjects employ in an effort to resist the oppressive and normalizing discourse of dominant ideology" (Muñoz 1999: 97). However, one can also detect a competing discourse in the data that sees Martin not as a powerless victim but as an artist who strategically uses sexual ambiguity as a selling tactic (19-21):

(19)

*Eleanor Moreno, 29, manager of the traditional Latin band Los Morenos, thinks Martin manipulates the **gay** debate to his advantage, making that mystique part of his image. "He's very clever about it," she said. "Is he **gay** or isn't he? He's riding that aura. It creates an erotic mystery -- [...]" [Calgary Herald, 11.03.2000]*

(20)

*[...] Martin comments. "Showbiz is about fantasy. You want to fantasize I'm **gay**? Go ahead. People can fantasize about me whatever way they want." [Globe and Mail, 26.06.1999]*

(21)

*[...] and he makes women swoon (while handling those **gay** rumours deftly enough to satisfy both those who want them to be true [...]" [Globe and Mail, 13.03.2000]*

5.3 Concordance lines of *homosexual** in AFTER

As noted in Section 5.1, the frequency of the more negative form *homosexual** has increased more strongly in AFTER, despite the text material being more recent. One reason could be that before the coming out, journalists who were negatively disposed towards gay people avoided writing about this topic altogether. This was no longer possible after Martin's coming out. At that point, even

journalists with a critical stance on same-sex sexualities had to address this topic. The following analysis of the usage patterns of *homosexual** in AFTER provides additional insights on this issue.

The form is still overwhelmingly used in negative contexts in AFTER, as illustrated below. It occurs regularly in syntactic proximity to semantically negative items or items that function as negative implication triggers. Typical patterns are, for example, the use of forms like *accept* or *acceptance* in connection with *homosexual**. This suggests that same-sex sexualities are intrinsically bad, of lesser value and not accepted by some parts of society (22), descriptions of institutions or societies that view same-sex sexualities as immoral, illegal or as something that should not be promoted (23-25), descriptions of being gay as detrimental to one's commercial success or career (26-27), or blaming the artist for hiding his sexual identification from the public for so long (28):

(22)

*New Gallup poll shows public acceptance of **homosexuality** among Americans is growing. 54% Find gay relations "morally acceptable"* [New York Post, 15.05.2012]

(23)

*Morocco's legal stance on **homosexuality** stems mostly from traditional Islamic morality, which considers both **homosexuality** and cross dressing as signs of immorality.* [US Official News, 22.07.2014]

(24)

*Martin was reportedly on an unofficial trip to the Qatari capital - many social media users zeroed in on the fact that the openly gay singer would visit a country that punishes **homosexuals**. However, the cultured star immersed himself in the culture by posting a photo of himself [...]* [Albawaba.com, 08.11.2015]

(25)

*Another religious leader on the island, Cardinal Luis Aponte Martinez of San Juan, has also criticised Martin and has asked him to stop promoting his **homosexuality**.* [New Musical Express, 14.04.2011]

(26)

*In the realms of chart-friendly pop, **homosexuality** has proved a particular thorn in the side for music executives.* [Independent, 31.03.2010]

(27)

*The message that Martin's story imparts is that **homosexuality** is a career-killer when it comes to pop music - that it is more acceptable in the 21st century to be a drug addict like Amy Winehouse or Pete Doherty than it is to be gay.* [Independent, 31.03.2010]

(28)

*Why is he only revealing his **homosexuality** now, after more than 10 years in the music business?* [Telegraph.co.uk, 30.03.2010]

These usages are similarly negative as those found in BEFORE, that is, they are an expression of heteronormativity as a powerful discourse that affects social actors both before and after their coming out.

Still, there is also some evidence that the journalists writing the text material in AFTER show some sensitivity to the negative connotations of the term *homosexual**. Usages like those illustrated above, in which it is the text author that can be held responsible for choosing the term, are not the only major usage type in AFTER. Another common usage is associated with journalists drawing on quotes as a distancing strategy, that is, they use the term *homosexual** in a way that suggests that other people have used it and that the use in the respective article is, therefore, just a secondary use. Many articles, for example, reproduce Martin's utterances as direct quotes, thus attributing the use of the term to him (29-30):

(29)

*[...] his blog post writing, "I am proud to say that I am a fortunate **homosexual** man. I am very blessed to be who I am."* [Contra Costa Times, 29.03.2010]

(30)

*I have decided to tell the world that I accept my **homosexuality** and celebrate this gift that life has given me. Now I feel strong. Free.* [El Paso Times, 22.04.2011]

These direct quotes are remarkable, because the term *homosexual** is used as an affirmative self-identifying label, which has the heteronormative effect that Ricky Martin is shown to construct his sexual identity in a distanced fashion (by means of a pathologising, technical term).

In numerous other articles, Martin's utterances are not directly quoted but reported on, that is, we find a third person construction that otherwise uses the same wording as Martin's quote (31-33):

(31)

*Since coming out as "a fortunate **homosexual** man" (his term) two months ago, Martin, 38, a dad whose twin sons Valentino and Matteo [...]* [Daily News New York, 30.05.2010]

(32)

*San Juan, March 30 -- Puerto Rican singer Ricky Martin has revealed that he is a **homosexual** and feels "blessed" to be himself.* [Indo-Asian News Service, 30.03.2010]

(33)

*[...] disseminated the news that Martin was that day accepting his (hitherto technically unacknowledged) **homosexuality** as a gift that life has given him.* [Guardian, 03.04.2010]

The self-distancing usages of *homosexual** may be due to the fact that the artist uttered them as part of his coming out or very shortly afterwards, possibly before he had developed a routine of talking positively about his same-sex identification in public. The term *homosexual* is

nowadays generally used as an out-group label, by heterosexual language users who describe gay people in a distancing fashion. Martin may at this point have been influenced by out-group language use about himself. As a native speaker of Spanish, he may also not have been fully aware of the connotations of the term in English. Moreover, the pathologising self-identifications dovetail with Martin's confessions to the press after his coming out that he used to have "internalised homophobia" and even bullied other gay people during his adolescence (34-35):

(34)

"I look back now and realise I would bully people who I knew were gay," he said. "I had internalised homophobia. To realise that was confronting to me. [Belfast Telegraph Online, 27.08.2013]

(35)

HE CAME out as gay in 2010 but Ricky Martin admits he used to be a homophobic "bully" struggling to deal with his own sexuality. [Express Online, 28.03.2013]

That quotes incorporating the term *homosexual** are selected and reproduced by journalists can be viewed as a strategy to associate the artist with the negative messages conveyed by the term without taking responsibility for it.

There are also some direct quotes of Martin's utterances in AFTER that date from the time before his coming out and clearly attest to the use of *homosexual** as a distancing device, as they form part of his earlier denials to the press (36):

(36)

*[...] and claimed that he is not gay. 'While I am very supportive of the **homosexual** community' I am not a **homosexual** myself' [Hindustan Times, 03.04.2010]*

Another quotative usage strategy involves reproducing utterances of other people that contain the term *homosexual** (even though it is not fully clear whether the original utterance really had incorporated the term or whether the wording has been adapted by the journalist; 37). These uses may not directly refer to Martin, but are often part of a more general discussion of same-sex sexualities in articles about the artist:

(37)

*[...] Mejia for saying that she will not let her children grow up to be **homosexuals**. Mejia, who upset gay groups with her public comments, [...] [Asian News International, 20.07.2012]*

What all secondary usage types of *homosexual** have in common is that they make it harder to blame the respective journalist for using this term. Thus, they pay witness to the problematic connotations that the term possesses.

5.4 Concordance lines of **gay** in AFTER

While the use of *homosexual** is equally negative and heteronormative in BEFORE and AFTER, the use of *gay* in AFTER is clearly less heteronormative than in BEFORE. The term is frequently used in semantically highly positive contexts, for example, co-occurring with positive terms such as *eligible*, *bachelor*, and *superstar* (38), or *joyfully*, *embrace*, *worth* and *celebrating* (39):

(38)

*AS the most eligible **gay** bachelor in the world, it's an understatement to say Latin superstar RICKY MARTIN has no shortage of potential partners.* [The Sun England, 27.05.2015]

(39)

*He said the secret had over time become "too heavy for me to keep inside" and that he joyfully embraces his **gay** identity as "something worth celebrating."* [Daily News Egypt, 30.03.2010]

Moreover, the adjective *gay* co-occurs with numerous personal nouns, none of which is semantically negative. Even though many of these noun phrases are not used to refer to Martin, they do have a cumulative effect of normalising the membership of gay people across various social groups. For example, *gay* co-occurs with nouns like *actors*, *artists*, *celebrity*, *celebrities*, *child*, *couples*, *donors*, *entertainers*, *fans*, *film historian*, *footballer*, *friends*, *Grammy winner*, *Latinas*, *Latinos*, *leading men*, *Olympian*, *stars*, *talent show graduate*, *teenagers* in AFTER. Note that many of these are plural forms, so they do not just refer to an individual social actor but to a whole group of gay referents.

At the same time, many of the syntactic contexts in which *gay* appears construct Ricky Martin's persona in a homonormative fashion, that is, as a positive example of a gay man who is out and open about his sexuality, a father treasuring family values (both 40), a married man (41), and a social actor who works as an activist for LGBT issues (42), is part of the gay community (43), and acts as a role model for other gay people (45):

(40)

*[...] an artist, a celebrity and, perhaps most importantly, a father who happens to be **gay**. "His decision to model this kind of openness and honesty can lead to greater acceptance for countless **gay** people in U.S., in Latin America and worldwide."* [WENN Entertainment News Wire Service, 30.03.2010]

(41)

*[...] claimed that Martin had secured Spanish citizenship in order to wed Abella under Spanish **gay** marriage laws.* [Asian News International, 04.01.2012]

(42)

*[...] his career, raising conjecture about his sexual orientation. In 2010 he announced that he was **gay** and has been an active advocate for gay rights, speaking at a UN conference [...]* [Jerusalem Post, 01.09.2016]

(43)

*Martin has revealed that he no longer feels lonely after revealing that he is **gay** because he feels "protected" by the love from the **gay** community.* [Asian News International, 05.07.2011]

(44)

*[...] TV interview with Oprah Winfrey and since then, he has been heralded as a **gay** role model, especially for Latin Americans.* [Shanghai Daily, 20.03.2011]

What these examples show is that normativity still plays a role in the use of *gay* as a descriptor for Martin after his coming out. However, it is now rather homonormativity than heteronormativity that is conveyed by them, since they are used to construct the artist as a positive example of a gay man who is well adjusted to the (heterosexual, white) US American mainstream. In other words, the way the news media construct Martin's persona renders his queer potential limited.

The discursive construction of homonormativity via the term *gay* does not just affect Martin's persona as such. It also pertains to his coming out, which is generally described as a positive, beneficial experience, for example, as a relief from torments or a liberation from the confusions of a closeted life (45-46):

(45)

*Ricky Martin has revealed that his life was 'very confusing' before he came out as a **gay**, as he had to show his false interest in women in order to maintain his pop star persona.* [Asian News International, 12.08.2011]

(46)

*Ricky announced he was **gay** in 2010 and in 2014 he discussed his relief at sharing the news.* [MailOnline, 18.04.2016]

Queer potential can only rarely be found in the usage of *gay* in AFTER. Only one instance can be identified in which the term is used in a more questioning fashion in AFTER, again in a direct quote by Martin (47):

(47)

[...] I'm against sexual labels, we are simply human beings with emotional and sexual needs. "I am gay, men fascinate me, but I like to enjoy sex in total freedom, so I'm open to having sex with a woman if I feel desire." [WENN Entertainment News Wire Service, 21.01.2016]

Even though Martin uses *gay* as an identity label here, he deconstructs it at the same time by drawing on an argument that positions sexual practices (*I like to enjoy sex in total freedom*) as independent of sexual desire (*men fascinate me*) and sexual identity (*I am gay*). In this passage, Martin thus refuses to be pinned down by dominant binary sexuality-related discourses (see also Calafell 2007: 108).

Table 4: Usage patterns of *gay* and *homosexual** in BEFORE and AFTER

	BEFORE	AFTER
<i>homosexual*</i>	negative contexts conveying heteronormativity	negative contexts conveying heteronormativity secondary quotative usages (distancing)
<i>gay</i>	contexts of sexual policing conveying heteronormativity	more positive contexts normalising usages conveying homonormativity

6 Conclusion

This study scrutinised the discursive construction of a celebrity before and after his coming out in the media. Through a basic quantitative and an in-depth qualitative analysis of usage patterns, it was shown that, rather than the discursive construction of the social actor becoming less normative, shifts in the quality of normative mechanisms surface in the data. The findings concerning the discursive construction of Ricky Martin’s persona do not support a strictly binary picture of (public) norm-conformity in the pre-coming-out and non-normativity in the post-coming out phase, nor do they suggest a strict in vs. out of the closet demarcation line. Rather, they suggest a gradual qualitative shift from mainly heteronormative mechanisms to a greater visibility of homonormative mechanisms and show the critical role of the media in the construction and perpetuation of normativity.

Ricky Martin’s coming out is clearly not representative of most non-heterosexual people’s coming out experiences. Due to his celebrity status, Martin operates from a privileged position, which ultimately gives his coming out the potential to influence social realities on a global scale. Contrary to most people’s coming out experiences, Martin’s public coming out cannot convincingly be viewed as part of a longer process of continued coming out events (on the processual nature of coming out, see Wong 2009: 12-15). Rather, it marks the endpoint of such a process. Whereas ordinary people have to go through coming out on a regular basis in front of different audiences throughout their lives, Martin is unlikely to undergo such processes further, as his identification as a gay man has become publicly known across the globe.

Despite the atypical character of Ricky Martin’s coming out, this study has provided valuable insights into the discursive effects of coming out. The qualitative analysis of concordance lines of the terms *gay* and *homosexual** in a corpus of news reports on Ricky Martin has shown that the functional usage patterns of these terms exhibit both similarities and differences in the media coverage before and after the artist’s public coming out as a gay man. Central patterns are summarised in Table 4. Both terms were predominantly used in a heteronormative, often negative fashion before the coming out. After the coming out, it is mainly *homosexual** that still exhibits these negative usages, beside secondary quotative usages that serve to distance authors from the term or to avoid taking responsibility for

using it. The term *gay*, by contrast, after the coming out is widely employed to construct more positive, normalised and homonormative images both of Martin and his coming out.

The linguistic evidence adduced here suggests that the claiming of a non-normative sexual identity may be associated with shifts in sexual normativity. Additionally, it suggests that coming out subjects people to the normative mechanisms associated with the newly claimed identity category (homonormativity). At the same time, heteronormative pressures do not disappear after coming out, but they become less dominant and face greater competition from homonormative discourses. The latter clearly surface in the discursive construction of Martin by the media after his coming out. They include descriptions of the artist as being in stable relationships (married), a father of two sons, politically active, a member of the gay community and a role model for other gay people. In other words, he is portrayed as the stereotype of a well-integrated gay man. To use Warner's definition of "good gays": Martin is described as "the kind [of gay man] who would not challenge the norms of straight culture, who would not flaunt sexuality, and who would not insist on living differently from ordinary folk." (Warner 1999: 113)

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